

A Hybrid System for Automatic Generation and Validation of Algerian Encyclopedic Content Using LLMs

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1. Abstract

The development of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT has led to significant advances in automatic content generation. However, their application in specific contexts, such as the creation of an Algerian encyclopedic dictionary, requires finetuning the models to ensure the relevance, accuracy, and coherence of the generated content.

This project is part of an explainable AI approach, where mechanisms are developed to structure the generated information and validate it in collaboration with experts. The system aims to enrich the Algerian cultural heritage database while integrating modern natural language processing techniques to ensure consistency and reliability in content generation.

Keywords : Web Scraping, Multilinguisme, Large Language Models, Collaborative Validation.

2. Introduction

Algeria has a very rich and diverse heritage, it includes tangible elements like monuments and artifacts and (for example

the Casbah of Algiers), as well as intangible elements (music, culture),

While there has been a significant progress in natural language generation (NLG) using large language models, these models are still limited when it comes to producing culturally relevant and good content about the Algerian heritage. Most models are not adapted to the local context, and the availability of structured, multilingual data related to Algeria is still very low. As a result, existing systems struggle to generate encyclopedic articles that are both informative and stylistically appropriate.

This project was developed in response to these gaps. Our goal is to build a system capable to generate cultural, multilingual content about our heritage, and ensure the quality through a hybrid method, combining automatic and expert human evaluation.

3. State of the art

To situate our work in relation with existing studies, we analyse some systems focused on content generation or automated content management, particularly, those related to the Algerian culture, or LLMs. Even though, no previous work has explored the combination of multilingual text generation, cultural specificity and human evaluation in the context of the Algerian context.

We mention briefly, **ArchGPT**(2024), which is an AI agent designed to generate specialized content using LLMs [1] , **Writesonic** (2020), a multilingual generation platform based on gpt models, we also considered **Hadretna** which is an Algerian initiative focused on the Algerian dialects using web scraping for culturally oriented generation [2] .

and finally, **Wikipedia**, although rich in cultural information, relies on user contributions rather than automated generation.

The following table provides a comparative overview between our solution and the existing works:

	Web scraping	Content generation -with LLMs	multilingualism	Collaborative validation	Algerian context
ArchGPT	no	yes	no	no	no
Writesonic	no	yes	yes	no	no
Hadretna	yes	no	ar	no	yes
Wikipedia	no	no	yes	yes	partial
Our solution	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

So , this comparison highlights the gap that we aim to fill, there are for we combined web scraping, content generation using LLMs , multilingualism, collaborative validation focusing on the Algerian cultural heritage.

4. Methodology and experiments:

Our methodology begins with the collection of a multilingual corpus from well-known sources, then we perform fine tuning of large language models to adapt them to the Algerian context.

Once the articles are generated, we assess their quality through a dual validation process with a human evaluation (by experts) and an automatic evaluation (using metrics).

4.1 Web scraping

We collected articles from various online sources related to the Algerian heritage, written in both languages Arabic and French. These articles covered multiple domains such as art, history...etc. during selections we ensured that all articles were faithful to the Algerian identity.

This is what we got:

Type de dataset	JSONL file	
size	fr	179 article
	ar	111 article
input	fr	Rédiger un article détaillé sur : [topic]
	ar	اكتب مقالة مفصلة حول : [topic]
output	The generated article	

Since datasets are so small , they are not sufficient to adapt large language models, we applied data augmentation techniques

to enhance the volume and diversity of the training data [3].

4.2 Data augmentation techniques:

-Back translation:

it consists of translating an article into another language, then translating it back into the original language using **googletrans** library, this process generates automatic reformulations, or paraphrases [4].

-Synonym replacement using AWN:

enrich our dataset and introduce variety in the text formulations, we used **arabic wordnet** to replace certain words with culturally relevant synonyms . this approach enhances arabic vocabulary diversity while maintaining semantic coherence [4].

-Random insertion of frequent words

this method consists of randomly inserting frequent words at different positions within the text. it helps introduce slight stylistic variations without altering the overall meaning of the content.

the augmentation techniques were applied separately to each dataset and to each section of the text (introduction, body, and conclusion). for every original entry, between 4 and 5 augmented variants were generated. a systematic check was performed to avoid duplicates, and the final files were saved in **jsonl** format while preserving the original data structure.

language	Applied Enrichment Techniques	Dataset size
ar	Random insertion of frequent words - Synonym replacement using Arabic WordNet Back-translation	600 unique article templates in Arabic
fr	Back-translation using English, German, and Spanish as pivot language	543 unique article templates in Arabic

4.3 Fine tuning des LLMs:

we used three different llms for generation tasks: a fine-tuned gpt-2 model (french), a t5-base model (arabic), and mistral-7b-instruct for bilingual generation. each model was fine-tuned on our enriched dataset using the transformers library.

the fine-tuning was conducted with a grid search :

Parameters	Values
Learning rate	0.0003, 0.0005
Batch size	2
Époches	6, 8

training was done on kaggle :

as shown in figure 2, the training and validation loss curves for the t5-small model are close, indicating good convergence and limited overfitting. the best configuration was achieved with 8 epochs and a learning rate of 0.0005.

The model achieved its best performance with **learning rate 0.0005** and **8 epochs**, reaching a training loss of **1.53** and validation loss of **1.62**. this setting showed clear improvement and good generalization, without signs of overfitting.

the gpt-2-fr model showed very low training loss, suggesting overfitting. with **learning rate 0.0003** and **8 epochs**, it

achieved the most stable validation loss (**1.27**), indicating a better balance between learning and generalization.

the arat5-base model, due to its larger size, showed initially high loss values. increasing the epochs and using **learning rate 0.0005** led to better performance. the best configuration (**8 epochs**) reached a training loss of **2.91** and validation loss of **2.67**, indicating good generalization without major overfitting.

aragpt2-base model reached very low training loss (as low as **0.58**), but validation loss remained relatively high (**~2.52–2.78**), suggesting potential overfitting, especially with higher learning rates. the best compromise was with **learning rate 0.0005** and **8 epochs**, achieving a validation loss of **2.52**, though still weaker than arat5.

4.4 model evaluation

4.4.1 evaluation methodology

large language models have the ability to generate text that closely resembles

human writing. however, to determine whether these models are truly effective — especially for generating encyclopedic content — a proper evaluation and comparison are essential.

in our case, we adopted a **multi-dimensional evaluation approach**, combining:

4.4.1.1 quantitative metrics

quantitative metrics are objective measures used to evaluate the performance of text generation models. they allow for reproducible and mathematically grounded comparison between different models.

-perplexity:

this metric measures the uncertainty of a language model in predicting the next word in a sequence. lower perplexity indicates better adaptation to the target language (in this case, french or arabic).

-BLEUScore [5]:

this metric evaluates the precision of n-grams in the generated text compared to a reference, with a brevity penalty applied to overly short outputs.

-ROUGE-Lscore[6]:

this metric assesses the quality of generated text based on the longest

common subsequence (LCS) between the generated output and the reference

4.4.1.2 Human evaluation :

this approach follows the human-in-the-loop principle, where human expertise remains central to the evaluation process ensuring that what the model produces is not only technically correct, but also contextually relevant, culturally faithful, and rich in meaning.

it is this iterative loop between machine and human judgment that allows us to produce truly solid, high-quality content [8].

human experts were asked to evaluate the generated articles based on five key criteria: cultural relevance, historical accuracy, logical structure, encyclopedic style, and linguistic fluency. each article was reviewed on these dimensions using a scoring grid, with special attention given to cultural and historical authenticity.

4.4.2 results of model evaluation

we present here the results of the comparative evaluation of the different models, following our defined evaluation protocol. the assessment is based on both quantitative metrics, computed on test sets of increasing size (50, then 100 articles), and qualitative analysis conducted by subject-matter experts.

by combining these two sources numerical scores on one side, and expert judgment on the other ,we were able to identify the model that performed best for the task of generating articles about algerian cultural heritage.

this model, which achieved the highest performance in both content quality and form, was selected for the next phase of the project.

4.4.2.1 quantitative results

we evaluated model performance , the metrics were computed separately for each language, in order to account for the linguistic differences between French and Arabic.

the following figures present the results obtained , we begin with the models fine-tuned on the French dataset, along with a detailed analysis of the scores for each metric.

fr-gpt2 achieved the best results, with the lowest perplexity (3.56) and the highest BLEU (0.25) and ROUGE-L (0.47) scores. this suggests high accuracy and alignment with reference texts. t5-base and t5-small showed lower performance, with higher perplexity and weaker BLEU/ROUGE scores, making them less suitable for structured French content generation.

according to the previous histogram, **arat5-base** showed weak performance, with high perplexity (**14.44**) and very low **BLEU** (~0.004) and **ROUGE-L** (<0.002), indicating poor accuracy. in contrast, **aragpt2-base** achieved better balance, with lower perplexity (**12.49**) and moderate **BLEU** (~0.07) and **ROUGE-L** (~0.19) scores.

4.4.2.2 qualitative results

to assess the true quality of the generated articles, we went beyond automatic metrics and involved two experts in Algerian heritage. their deep understanding of history, traditions, and language allowed for a culturally grounded evaluation.

each article was scored independently by both experts across the five criteria described in section 4.3, using a 5-point scale. individual scores were averaged per criterion, and a global score was computed for each article.

this human-centered evaluation provided nuanced feedback beyond what automated metrics can capture, helping ensure that the generated texts were not only technically correct, but also meaningful, credible, and culturally respectful.

Model	final overall average
fr	
Small-T5	2.062
T5-base	2.674
Frgpt-2	2.892
ar	
T5-ar-base	0.96
Ar-gpt2-base	2.12

so, human evaluation results confirm the findings from the automatic metrics, for frenchmodels, fr-gpt2 achieved the highest overall average (2.89), followed by t5-base (2.67) and small-t5 (2.06).

for arabic models, aragpt2-base has the higher score (2.12 vs. 0.96).

these results show that gpt2 models produce more coherent and culturally relevant content.

combined scores :

when combining both automatic and human evaluation results[9], **fr-gpt2** stands out as the top-performing french model, it achieves the lowest perplexity (3.56), the highest BLEU and ROUGE scores (0.25 / 0.47), and the best expert score (2.89).

for arabic, aragpt2-**base** out performs arat5-base in all dimensions, it shows better perplexity (12.49 vs. 14.44), significantly higher BLEU/ROUGE scores (0.07 / 0.19), and a human evaluation average (2.12 vs. 0.96).

these results confirm the superiority of gpt-style models for multilingual article

generation and support their selection for the next stage of our work

Final choice:

based on the combined scores, which account for both quantitative and qualitative evaluation, fr-gpt2 emerged as the most effective model for french article generation.

similarly, aragpt2-base was identified as the best-performing model for arabic, achieving the highest overall score across all evaluation criteria.

5. Optional enhancement and extentions

as an exploratory step, we integrated a sentiment analysis component using pretrained transformers to evaluate expert reviews, this aims to accelerate the human evaluation process in large-scale applications by providing rapid sentiment insights.

additionally, we tested an active learning loop that uses uncertainty scores to prioritize low-quality articles (based on human reviews) for targeted retraining, this selective feedback mechanism was

designed to improve fluency and cultural alignment over time.

while these components were not part of the core generation pipeline, they open promising directions for future refinement and feedback-driven optimization.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we explored the use of large language models to generate encyclopedic content about algerian cultural heritage in arabic and french. we collected and enriched a multilingual dataset, applied fine-tuning to several transformer-based models, and conducted both automatic and expert-based evaluations.

we are aware of the limitations of this work, particularly related to the size and diversity of the training datasets, which impact the models' ability to generalize. however, the proposed pipeline sets a solid foundation for future research in culturally grounded multilingual generation.

results show that gpt-style models, especially fr-gpt2 and aragpt2-base, outperform t5 variants in both fluency and cultural relevance. this confirms the value of model adaptation and human-in-the-loop evaluation when working on sensitive cultural content.

7. Future works

the future, we aim to expand the system to support other languages spoken in algeria, including tamazight and darija, as well as english. we also plan to build a larger and more diverse corpus by integrating content from books and academic publications. improvements in data cleaning through

named entity recognition (NER), and the use of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) for more accurate, well-sourced texts are also planned. finally, we hope to strengthen human involvement, improve article structure, and extend the system to real-world applications in education, museums, and cultural outreach.

8. References

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